

Primitive equation in pressure coordinate

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + u \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} + \omega \frac{\partial u}{\partial p} - f v = -\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial x} - \frac{u}{a}$$

$$\frac{\partial v}{\partial t} + u \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} + \omega \frac{\partial v}{\partial p} + f u = -\frac{\partial \phi}{\partial y} - \frac{v}{a}$$

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial p} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \zeta_2}{\partial t} + u \frac{\partial \zeta_2}{\partial x} + v \frac{\partial \zeta_2}{\partial y} + \omega \frac{\partial \zeta_2}{\partial p} = \zeta_x \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial x} + \zeta_y \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial y} + (f + \zeta_2) \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial p} - \frac{\zeta_2}{a}$$

$$\frac{\partial \zeta_2}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x}(u \zeta_2) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y}(v \zeta_2) - \zeta_2 \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} \right) + \omega \frac{\partial \zeta_2}{\partial p} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x}(\zeta_x \omega) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y}(\zeta_y \omega) + \omega \frac{\partial \zeta_2}{\partial x} + \omega \frac{\partial \zeta_2}{\partial y} + \zeta_2 \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial p} + f \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial p} - \frac{\zeta_2}{a}$$

$$\frac{\partial \zeta_2}{\partial t} + \nabla_h \cdot (\vec{u}_h \zeta_2) = \nabla_h \cdot (\vec{\zeta}_h \omega) + f \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial p} - \frac{\zeta_2}{a}$$

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial p} = 0$$

$$\frac{\partial \zeta_x}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \zeta_y}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial \zeta_2}{\partial p} = 0, \quad \zeta_x = \frac{\partial v}{\partial p}, \quad \zeta_y = -\frac{\partial u}{\partial p}, \quad \zeta_2 = \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial u}{\partial y}$$

$$\frac{\partial \zeta_x}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \zeta_y}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial \zeta_2}{\partial p} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\frac{\partial v}{\partial p} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(-\frac{\partial u}{\partial p} \right) - \frac{\partial}{\partial p} \left(\frac{\partial v}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \right) = 0$$

Cylindrical coordinate, axis symmetry

$$\frac{\partial \zeta_2}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r}(r u_r \zeta_2) = \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial}{\partial r}(r \zeta_r \omega) + f \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial p} - \frac{\zeta_2}{a}$$

$$\frac{\partial \zeta_2}{\partial t} + u_r \frac{\partial \zeta_2}{\partial r} + \zeta_2 \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial r} + \frac{u_r \zeta_2}{r} = \zeta_r \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial r} + \omega \frac{\partial \zeta_r}{\partial r} + \frac{\zeta_r \omega}{r} + f \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial p} - \frac{\zeta_2}{a}$$

$$\zeta_r = \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial p}, \quad \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial r} + \frac{u_r}{r} + \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial p} = 0$$

$$\zeta_2 = \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial r} + \frac{u_\theta}{r}$$

$$\frac{\partial \zeta_2}{\partial t} + u_r \frac{\partial \zeta_2}{\partial r} + \zeta_2 \left(\frac{\partial u_r}{\partial r} + \frac{u_r}{r} \right) = \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial p} \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial r} + \omega \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(\frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial p} \right) + \omega \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial p} + f \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial p} - \frac{\zeta_2}{a}$$

$$\frac{\partial \zeta_2}{\partial t} + u_r \frac{\partial \zeta_2}{\partial r} - \zeta_2 \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial p} = \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial p} \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial r} + \omega \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(\frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial r} + \frac{u_\theta}{r} \right) + f \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial p} - \frac{\zeta_2}{a}$$

$$\frac{\partial \zeta_2}{\partial t} + u_r \frac{\partial \zeta_2}{\partial r} + \omega \frac{\partial \zeta_2}{\partial p} = \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial p} \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial r} + (f + \zeta_2) \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial p} - \frac{\zeta_2}{a}$$

$$\frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial t} = -\nabla_h \cdot [\vec{u}_h (\zeta + f)] + \nabla_h \cdot (\vec{\zeta}_h \omega)$$

convergence
tilting

$$-\nabla_h \cdot [\vec{u}_h (\zeta + f)] = \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial p} \frac{1}{S} \iint_S (\zeta + f) dS$$

$$\nabla_h \cdot (\vec{\zeta}_h \omega) = \frac{\partial}{\partial x}(\zeta_x \omega) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y}(\zeta_y \omega)$$

$$= \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(-\omega \frac{\partial v}{\partial p} \right) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} \left(\omega \frac{\partial u}{\partial p} \right) \quad \zeta_x = -\frac{\partial v}{\partial p}, \quad \zeta_y = \frac{\partial u}{\partial p}$$

$$= -\vec{k} \cdot \nabla \times \left(\omega \frac{\partial \vec{u}_h}{\partial p} \right)$$

$$\frac{1}{S} \iint_S \nabla_h \cdot (\vec{\zeta}_h \omega) dS = \frac{1}{S} \iint_S \vec{k} \cdot \nabla \times \left(\omega \frac{\partial \vec{u}_h}{\partial p} \right) dS$$

$$= -\frac{1}{S} \oint_C \omega \frac{\partial u_\theta}{\partial p} dl$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= -\frac{1}{s} \int_c \omega \frac{\partial U_0}{\partial p} dl \\
&\approx -\frac{1}{s} \omega \int_c \frac{\partial U_0}{\partial p} dl \\
&= -\omega \frac{\partial}{\partial p} \left(\frac{1}{s} \int_c U_0 dl \right) \\
&= -\omega \frac{\partial \zeta}{\partial p}
\end{aligned}$$

Appendix A.

$$\check{t} = ft, \quad \check{p} = \frac{p}{\rho_0 U_0^2}, \quad \check{\zeta}_2 = \frac{L}{U_0} \zeta_2, \quad \check{\omega} = \frac{L}{\rho_0 U_0^3} \omega, \quad \check{c}_d = fLd$$

$$\omega \sim \frac{\rho_0 U_0^2}{L} \sim \frac{\rho_0 U_0^3}{L}$$

$$\Rightarrow \frac{\partial \check{\zeta}_2}{\partial \check{t}} \cdot \frac{U_0}{L} \cdot \frac{1}{f} + \check{\omega} \cdot \frac{\rho_0 U_0^3}{L} \frac{\partial \frac{U_0}{L} \check{\zeta}_2}{\rho_0 U_0^2 \partial \check{p}} = f \frac{\rho_0 U_0^3}{L} \frac{\partial \check{\omega}}{\partial \rho_0 U_0^2 \partial \check{p}} + \frac{U_0}{L} \check{\zeta}_2 \cdot \frac{\partial \rho_0 U_0^3 / L \check{\omega}}{\partial \rho_0 U_0^2 \partial \check{p}} - \frac{U_0}{L} \frac{\check{\zeta}_2}{f}$$

$$\Rightarrow \frac{\partial \check{\zeta}_2}{\partial \check{t}} \cdot \frac{f U_0}{L} + \check{\omega} \cdot \frac{\partial \check{\zeta}_2}{\partial \check{p}} \cdot \frac{U_0^2}{L^2} = f \frac{U_0}{L} \frac{\partial \check{\omega}}{\partial \check{p}} + \frac{U_0^2}{L^2} \check{\zeta}_2 \frac{\partial \check{\omega}}{\partial \check{p}} - \frac{f U_0}{L} \frac{\check{\zeta}_2}{f}$$

$$\Rightarrow \frac{\partial \check{\zeta}_2}{\partial \check{t}} + \check{\omega} \frac{\partial \check{\zeta}_2}{\partial \check{p}} \cdot \frac{U_0}{fL} = \frac{\partial \check{\omega}}{\partial \check{p}} + \check{\zeta}_2 \frac{\partial \check{\omega}}{\partial \check{p}} - \frac{\check{\zeta}_2}{f}$$

We let $\epsilon \equiv \frac{U_0}{fL} \ll 1$

$$\check{\zeta}_2 = \epsilon^0 \check{\zeta}_2^{(0)} + \epsilon^1 \check{\zeta}_2^{(1)} + \dots$$

$$\check{\omega} = \epsilon^0 \check{\omega}^{(0)} + \epsilon^1 \check{\omega}^{(1)}$$

$$\Rightarrow \epsilon^0: \frac{\partial \check{\zeta}_2^{(0)}}{\partial \check{t}} + \frac{\check{\zeta}_2^{(0)}}{\check{c}_d} = \frac{\partial \check{\omega}^{(0)}}{\partial \check{p}}$$

$$\epsilon^1: \frac{\partial \check{\zeta}_2^{(1)}}{\partial \check{t}} + \frac{\check{\zeta}_2^{(1)}}{\check{c}_d} = \check{\zeta}_2^{(0)} \frac{\partial \check{\omega}^{(0)}}{\partial \check{p}} - \check{\omega}^{(0)} \frac{\partial \check{\zeta}_2^{(0)}}{\partial \check{p}} + \frac{\partial \check{\omega}^{(1)}}{\partial \check{p}}$$

Appendix B

$$\frac{\partial \check{\zeta}_2^{(0)}}{\partial \check{t}} + \frac{\check{\zeta}_2^{(0)}}{\check{c}_d} = f \frac{\partial \check{\omega}^{(0)}}{\partial \check{p}} \Rightarrow \check{\zeta}_2^{(0)} = f \frac{d\check{\omega}^{(0)}}{d\check{p}} \int_0^{\check{t}} \Delta \omega(t') e^{-\frac{\check{t}-t'}{\check{c}_d}} dt'$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial \check{\zeta}_2^{(1)}}{\partial \check{t}} + \frac{\check{\zeta}_2^{(1)}}{\check{c}_d} &= -\omega^{(0)} \frac{\partial \check{\zeta}_2^{(0)}}{\partial \check{p}} + \check{\zeta}_2^{(0)} \frac{\partial \check{\omega}^{(0)}}{\partial \check{p}} + f \frac{\partial \check{\omega}^{(1)}}{\partial \check{p}} \\
&= f \Delta \omega(t) \left[-\check{\omega} \frac{d^2 \check{\omega}}{d\check{p}^2} + \left(\frac{d\check{\omega}}{d\check{p}} \right)^2 \right] \int_0^{\check{t}} \Delta \omega(t') e^{-\frac{\check{t}-t'}{\check{c}_d}} dt' \\
&= f \Delta \omega(t) \left[-\frac{d}{d\check{p}} \left(\check{\omega} \frac{d\check{\omega}}{d\check{p}} \right) + 2 \left(\frac{d\check{\omega}}{d\check{p}} \right)^2 \right] \int_0^{\check{t}} \Delta \omega(t') e^{-\frac{\check{t}-t'}{\check{c}_d}} dt'
\end{aligned}$$

$$\frac{d \check{\zeta}_2^{(1)}}{d\check{t}} + \frac{\check{\zeta}_2^{(1)}}{\check{c}_d} = 2 \left(\frac{d\check{\omega}}{d\check{p}} \right)^2 f \Delta \omega \int_0^{\check{t}} \Delta \omega(t') e^{-\frac{\check{t}-t'}{\check{c}_d}} dt'$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\overline{S_2^{(1)}} &= 2f \left(\frac{d\Phi}{dp} \right)^2 \int_0^t \Delta\omega(t') e^{-\frac{t-t'}{T_d}} \left(\int_0^{t'} \Delta\omega(t'') e^{-\frac{t-t''}{T_d}} dt'' \right) dt' \\
&= 2f \left(\frac{d\Phi}{dp} \right)^2 \int_0^t \left(\int_0^{t'} \Delta\omega(t'') e^{-\frac{t-t''}{T_d}} dt'' \right) d \left(\int_0^{t'} \Delta\omega(t''') e^{-\frac{t-t'''}{T_d}} dt''' \right) \\
&= 2f \left(\frac{d\Phi}{dp} \right)^2 \int_0^t e^{-\frac{t-t'}{T_d}} \left(\int_0^{t'} \Delta\omega(t'') e^{-\frac{t-t''}{T_d}} dt'' \right) d \left(\int_0^{t'} \Delta\omega(t''') e^{-\frac{t-t'''}{T_d}} dt''' \right) \\
&\geq 2f \left(\frac{d\Phi}{dp} \right)^2 \int_0^t \left(\int_0^{t'} \Delta\omega(t'') e^{-\frac{t-t''}{T_d}} dt'' \right) d \left(\int_0^{t'} \Delta\omega(t''') e^{-\frac{t-t'''}{T_d}} dt''' \right) \\
&= f \left(\frac{d\Phi}{dp} \right)^2 \left(\int_0^t \Delta\omega(t'') e^{-\frac{t-t''}{T_d}} dt'' \right)^2
\end{aligned}$$

Appendix C

$$\frac{\partial \overline{S_2^{(1)}}}{\partial t} + \mathcal{U}_r^{(0)} \frac{\partial \overline{S_2^{(0)}}}{\partial r} + \omega^{(0)} \frac{\partial \overline{S_2^{(0)}}}{\partial p} = - \frac{\partial \mathcal{U}_0^{(0)}}{\partial p} \frac{\partial \omega^{(0)}}{\partial r} + \overline{S_2^{(0)}} \frac{\partial \omega^{(0)}}{\partial p} + f \frac{\partial \omega^{(0)}}{\partial p} - \frac{\overline{S_2^{(1)}}}{T_d}$$

$$\overline{S_2^{(0)}} = fR \frac{d\Phi}{dp} T_0(t)$$

$$\mathcal{U}_0^{(0)} = f \frac{d\Phi}{dp} \frac{1}{r} \int_0^r R r dr$$

$$\mathcal{U}_r^{(0)} = -\Delta\omega \frac{d\Phi}{dp} \frac{1}{r} \int_0^r R r dr$$

$$\omega^{(0)} = \Delta\omega \Xi(p) R(r)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{\partial \overline{S_2^{(1)}}}{\partial t} - \Delta\omega \frac{d\Phi}{dp} \frac{1}{r} \int_0^r R r dr \cdot f \frac{d\Phi}{dp} T_0(t) \frac{dR}{dr} + \Delta\omega \Xi R f R \frac{d^2\Phi}{dp^2} T_0(t) \\
= -f T_0 \frac{d^2\Phi}{dp^2} \frac{1}{r} \int_0^r R r dr \cdot \Delta\omega \Xi \frac{dR}{dr} + f R \frac{d\Phi}{dp} T_0(t) \Delta\omega \frac{d\Phi}{dp} R + f \frac{\partial \omega^{(0)}}{\partial p} - \frac{\overline{S_2^{(1)}}}{T_d} \\
\begin{matrix} \uparrow & & \uparrow \\ -\frac{\partial \mathcal{U}_0^{(0)}}{\partial p} \frac{\partial \omega^{(0)}}{\partial r} & & \overline{S_2^{(0)}} \frac{\partial \omega^{(0)}}{\partial p} \end{matrix}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{d}{dt} \overline{S_2^{(1)}} + \frac{\overline{S_2^{(1)}}}{T_d} &= \overline{f \left(\frac{d\Phi}{dp} \right)^2 \Delta\omega T_0 \cdot \frac{1}{r} \int_0^r R r dr \cdot \frac{dR}{dr}} - \overline{f \Xi \frac{d^2\Phi}{dp^2} \Delta\omega T_0 \cdot \frac{1}{r} \int_0^r R r dr \cdot \frac{dR}{dr}} \\
&\quad - \overline{f \Xi \frac{d^2\Phi}{dp^2} \Delta\omega T_0 \cdot R^2} + \overline{f \left(\frac{d\Phi}{dp} \right)^2 \Delta\omega T_0 \cdot R^2} \\
&\quad \begin{matrix} \uparrow & & \uparrow \\ -\omega^{(0)} \frac{\partial \overline{S_2^{(0)}}}{\partial p} & & \overline{S_2^{(0)}} \frac{\partial \omega^{(0)}}{\partial p} \end{matrix}
\end{aligned}$$

$$= 2f \left(\frac{d\Phi}{dp} \right)^2 \Delta\omega T_0 \cdot \frac{1}{r} \int_0^r R r dr \frac{dR}{dr} + 2f \left(\frac{d\Phi}{dp} \right)^2 \Delta\omega T_0 \cdot R^2$$

$$= 2f \left(\frac{d\Phi}{dp} \right)^2 \Delta\omega T_0 \left(\frac{1}{r} \int_0^r R r dr \frac{dR}{dr} + R^2 \right), \text{ let } M = \int_0^r R r dr, \quad R = \frac{1}{r} \frac{dM}{dr}$$

$$\text{at } r=0, \frac{dR}{dr} = 0, R=1 \quad \perp \int_0^r R r dr \cdot \frac{dR}{dr} + R^2$$

$$= \int_0^L \left(\frac{dM}{dr} \right) \Delta \omega \cdot r \left(\frac{1}{r} \int_0^r R r' dr' \right) dr, \text{ let } M = \int_0^r R r' dr, \quad R = \frac{1}{r} \frac{dM}{dr}$$

$$\text{at } r=0, \frac{dR}{dr} = 0, R=1$$

$$\frac{1}{r} \int_0^r R r' dr \cdot \frac{dR}{dr} + R^2$$

$$= \frac{M}{r} \frac{d}{dr} \left(\frac{1}{r} \frac{dM}{dr} \right) + \frac{1}{r^2} \left(\frac{dM}{dr} \right)^2$$

$$\text{Suppose } R = e^{-\frac{r^2}{L^2}}$$

$$M = \int_0^r R r' dr$$

$$= \int_0^r e^{-\frac{r'^2}{L^2}} r' dr$$

$$= \frac{L^2}{2} \int_0^{\frac{r^2}{L^2}} e^{-\frac{r'^2}{L^2}} d\left(\frac{r'^2}{L^2}\right)$$

$$= \frac{L^2}{2} \left(1 - e^{-\frac{r^2}{L^2}} \right)$$

$$M^2 = \frac{L^4}{4} \left(1 - e^{-\frac{r^2}{L^2}} \right)^2$$

$$= \frac{1}{r} \frac{d}{dr} \left(\frac{M}{r} \frac{dM}{dr} \right) - \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{dM}{dr} \frac{dM}{dr} + \frac{1}{r^2} \left(\frac{dM}{dr} \right)^2$$

$$= \frac{1}{r} \frac{d}{dr} \left(\frac{M}{r} \frac{dM}{dr} \right)$$

$$= \frac{d}{d(r^2/2)} \left(\frac{d(M^2/2)}{d(r^2/2)} \right)$$

$$= 2 \frac{d^2 M^2}{d(r^2)^2}$$

$$\frac{dM^2}{dr^2} = \frac{L^4}{4} 2 \left(1 - e^{-\frac{r^2}{L^2}} \right) (-1) \left(-\frac{2r}{L^2} \right) e^{-\frac{r^2}{L^2}}$$

$$= \frac{L^2}{2} \left(1 - e^{-\frac{r^2}{L^2}} \right) e^{-\frac{r^2}{L^2}}$$

$$= \frac{L^2}{2} e^{-\frac{r^2}{L^2}} - \frac{L^2}{2} e^{-\frac{2r^2}{L^2}}$$

$$R = e^{-\frac{r^2}{L^2}}$$

$$2 \frac{d^2 M^2}{d(r^2)^2} = L^2 \left(-\frac{2r}{L^2} \right) e^{-\frac{r^2}{L^2}} - L^2 \left(-\frac{4r}{L^2} \right) e^{-\frac{2r^2}{L^2}}$$

$$= -e^{-\frac{r^2}{L^2}} + 2e^{-\frac{2r^2}{L^2}}$$

$$= \underbrace{-e^{-\frac{r^2}{L^2}} + e^{-\frac{2r^2}{L^2}}}_{\frac{dR}{dr} \frac{1}{r} \int_0^r R r' dr} + \underbrace{e^{-\frac{2r^2}{L^2}}}_{R^2}$$

$$\frac{dR}{dr} \frac{1}{r} \int_0^r R r' dr = -\frac{2r}{L^2} e^{-\frac{r^2}{L^2}} \cdot \frac{1}{r} \cdot \frac{L^2}{2} \left(1 - e^{-\frac{r^2}{L^2}} \right)$$

$$= -e^{-\frac{r^2}{L^2}} + e^{-\frac{2r^2}{L^2}}$$

$$\text{inflection point: } \frac{de^{-\frac{r^2}{L^2}}}{dr} = -\frac{2r}{L^2} e^{-\frac{r^2}{L^2}}$$

$$\frac{d^2 e^{-\frac{r^2}{L^2}}}{dr^2} = -\frac{2}{L^2} e^{-\frac{r^2}{L^2}} \left(1 - \frac{r}{L^2} \cdot 2r \right)$$

$$= -\frac{2}{L^2} e^{-\frac{r^2}{L^2}} \left(1 - \frac{2r^2}{L^2} \right)$$

$$\Rightarrow \text{let } = 0, r = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{2} L$$

$$\text{let } \frac{d^2 M^2}{d(r^2)^2} = 0 \Rightarrow \frac{1}{2} e^{-\frac{r^2}{L^2}} = e^{-\frac{2r^2}{L^2}}$$

$$\Rightarrow \frac{1}{2} = e^{-\frac{r^2}{L^2}}$$

$$\Rightarrow -\ln 2 = -\frac{r^2}{L^2}$$

$$\Rightarrow r_c = L \underbrace{(\ln 2)^{1/2}}_{\approx 0.83}, \text{ halfwidth}$$

Rev radial: $R(r)$

$$\delta \text{ radial: } \frac{2 \frac{d^2 M^2}{d(r^2)^2}}{R(r)} = \frac{-e^{-\frac{r^2}{L^2}} + 2e^{-\frac{2r^2}{L^2}}}{e^{-\frac{r^2}{L^2}}}$$

$$= -1 + 2e^{-\frac{r^2}{L^2}}$$

$$\approx -1 + 2 \left(1 - \frac{r^2}{L^2} + 0(r^4) \right)$$

$$= 1 - \frac{2r^2}{L^2}$$

$$\delta = \delta|_{r=0} \times \frac{2 \frac{d^2 M^2}{d(r^2)^2}}{R(r)}$$

Appendix D

$$\widetilde{\int_2^{(1)} u} \sim \widetilde{2 \frac{d^2 m^2}{dV^2}} = \widetilde{(-e^{-\frac{r^2}{L^2}} + 2e^{-\frac{2r^2}{L^2}})} \sim -e^{-\frac{r^2}{L^2+lf^2}} \cdot \frac{L^2}{L^2+lf^2} + 2e^{-\frac{r^2}{L^2+lf^2}} \frac{L^2/2}{L^2+lf^2}$$

$$\widetilde{\int_2^{(1)} u}^{1/2} \sim \widetilde{R} \sim \frac{L^2}{L^2+lf^2} e^{-\frac{r^2}{L^2+lf^2}}$$

$$\Rightarrow \delta = \frac{\widetilde{\int_2^{(1)} u} \Big|_{r=0}}{\widetilde{\int_2^{(1)} u}^{1/2} \Big|_{r=0}} \cdot \frac{-\frac{L^2}{L^2+lf^2} + 2 \frac{L^2/2}{L^2+lf^2}}{\frac{L^2}{L^2+lf^2}}$$

$$\text{radial part} = -1 + \frac{L^2+lf^2}{L^2+lf^2}$$

$$= \frac{-L^2/2 - lf^2 + L^2 + lf^2}{L^2+lf^2}$$

$$= \frac{L^2/2}{L^2+lf^2}$$

$$= 1 - \frac{lf^2}{L^2+lf^2}$$

$$\frac{\delta}{R_{ov}} \sim \frac{1 - \frac{lf^2}{L^2+lf^2}}{\frac{L^2}{L^2+lf^2}}$$

$$= \frac{L^2/2}{L^2+lf^2}$$

$$= \frac{L^2}{L^2+lf^2}$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{L^2+lf^2}{\frac{L^2}{2} + lf^2}$$

$$= \frac{L^2+lf^2}{L^2+2lf^2}$$

$$= \frac{1 + \frac{lf^2}{L^2}}{1 + \frac{2lf^2}{L^2}}$$